

A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO THEIR GENDER, LOCALITY AND AGE

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Abstract

The study analyses the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers in relation to their gender, locality, and age. Three hundred and ten (310) secondary school teachers designed the sample to collect data from 24 secondary schools of various managements in East Godavari district of A.P. The researcher used the descriptive survey method. Emotional Intelligence scale is developed and standardized by AnuKool Hyde, Sanjyot Pethe, and Upinder Dhar (2004) was employed to collect data. This scale consists of 34 items. The split half method was adopted for calculation of reliability coefficient and the value was 0.88. To find the validity from the coefficient of reliability, the reliability index is calculated, which indicates a high validity as it is 0.93.

Keywords: *Emotional Intelligence and secondary school teachers.*

Introduction

Emotional intelligence is an urgent need of society. The need of the society is always fulfilled through the education system. The teacher is the pivot to any existing education system. Therefore, the teacher has a great role to play in developing emotional intelligence in children. He must design various operations and change the existing system to achieve the desired result. According to Minakshi and Santamu Kumar Swain (2009) in the article 'Emotional Intelligence and Teacher', some activities to enhance emotional intelligence are discussed. The main goal of education is the holistic development of students. In achieving this goal, teachers play an important role. Emotionally intelligent teachers help students with better motivation, better innovation, increased performance, efficient use of time and

resources, better leadership qualities and better team work. Therefore, it is very important to develop the emotional intelligence of student teachers during pre-service (as cited Amirtha, M. & Kadiravan, S. 2006).

Whether it's in the boardroom or the classroom, people need skills to communicate, work in teams and let go of personal and family problems that come along the way at work and learning, such skills contribute to what is called emotional intelligence, and they are even more important as educators realize that these skills are key to academic achievement. Mentally intelligent people stand out. Their ability to empathize, persevere, control impulses, communicate clearly, make thoughtful decisions, solve problems and work with others will gain friends and success; They live happier lives with more satisfying relationships. At work, they are more productive and they increase productivity in others. At school they work better on the standard test and help create a safe, comfortable classroom environment that makes learning easier, we all want to raise well-adjusted, happy and successful children. How do we improve the chances of raising children with these traits? One place to start is to find growing evidence that a person's "emotional intelligence" is of paramount importance, it is clear that having high emotional intelligence is a great assessment for job success and personal success. Emotional intelligence measures the characteristics of your feeling's perception, ability to empathize with other people, listening skills, and so on.

Meaning:

Mayer, John D. and Salovey, Peter (1990) defined emotional intelligence as “the subset of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one’s own and others feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one’s thinking and actions”. According to *Daniel Goleman and Mayer, John D., Emotional Intelligence (EI)* is the ability to monitor one’s own and other people’s emotions, to discriminate between different emotions and label them appropriately, and to use emotional information to guide thinking and behaviour (as cited Jyosthana, M, and Bhaskara Rao, D., 2016, pp.4-5).

Need for the Present Study

Teacher has a very pivotal role in the social reconstruction and in the transmission of wisdom, knowledge and experiences of one generation to another. Several scholars, educationalists like *Dr. S. Radhakrishnan* have stressed the importance of teachers in shaping the future generations. The teacher, his personal qualities, his educational qualification, his professional training and the place that he occupies in the school as well as in the community is of vital importance. The 21st century is witnessing not only an explosion of knowledge in

all the spheres of human endeavour. The socio, political and economic changes that are taking place demands corresponding changes in the sphere of education. Teachers are an integral part of the education system and so there is a need to draw new insights on the role of the teachers, their responsibilities, training requirements, in-service programmes etc. The present-day teacher is a multi-tasker. The understanding of some of the aspects like the work orientation of the teacher, personality traits, emotional intelligence of the teacher towards the profession etc. will help educational planners and managers to incorporate necessary and relevant mechanisms in the system to make teaching more effective and purposeful. It is decided to carry out the present study “a study on emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers in relation to their gender, locality and age” has been contemplated. It is assumed that the study would throw open new insights on the three aspects considered and the relation among them so that future teacher training programmes would gear up to the demands of the system.

Review of Related Literature

Srinivasa Rao, T. (2020) studied the work orientation of primary school teachers in relation to their value pattern and emotional intelligence. The investigator decided to select Visakhapatnam district of the 23 districts of Andhra Pradesh. There are three educational divisions, namely, Paderu, Yellamanchilli and Visakhapatnam and there are 43 mandalas. The investigator took 509 samples. Five mandalas from each division are selected through lottery method. Emotional Intelligence Scale developed and standardized by AnuKool Hyde, Sanjyot Pethe, and Upinder Dhar (2004) was employed in this study. This scale consists of 34 items. Results showed that gender, age, professional qualifications and teaching experience of the primary school teachers don't make significant difference in their emotional intelligence. *Sudha and Amaladoss, S. (2017)* studied on emotional intelligence and social achievement of higher secondary school students. The sample consisted of 350 higher secondary school students. Finding of the study revealed that there was no significant difference between male and female higher secondary school students in their emotional intelligence and its dimensions. *Bala Krishnan, V. and Velmurugan, K. (2016)* studied on emotional intelligence in higher secondary students of vocational stream. The findings found that there was a significant difference in the emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to their locality and income and there was no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to their type of family, caste, parental education and parental occupation. *Vijayalaxmi R Kore (2015)* studied on emotional

intelligence of student teachers in relation to self-concept and demographic variable. The results showed that the male and female student teachers differed significantly with respect to emotional intelligence, the male and female student teachers differed significantly with respect to dimensions of emotional intelligence, namely, emotional stability, managing relation, and value orientation and the male and female student teachers didn't differ significantly with respect to dimensions of emotional intelligence, namely, self-awareness, self-development, empathy, self-motivation, integration, commitment and altruistic behaviour respectively.

Statement of The Problem

Title of the present investigation is “*A study on emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers in relation to their gender, locality and age*”.

Methodology

Population:

Teachers working in secondary schools in East Godavari District constitute the population for this study.

Sample:

Three hundred and ten (310) secondary school teachers designed the sample to collect data from 24 secondary schools of various management in East Godavari district of A.P.

Tool used for this study

Emotional Intelligence scale is developed and standardized by AnuKool Hyde, Sanjyot Pethe, and Upinder Dhar (2004). This scale consists of 34 items. The items given in this scale have been designed to measure ten areas of emotional intelligence. They are self-awareness, empathy, self-motivation, emotional stability, managing relations, integrity, self-development, value orientation, commitment and altruistic behaviour. In this scale five-point scale is used. They are strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. Each statement should have a score of 5 to strongly agree, 4 to agree, 3 to neutral, 2 to disagree and 1 to strongly disagree. Scores range from 34 to 170. The split half method was adopted for calculation of reliability coefficient and the value was 0.88. To find the validity from the coefficient of reliability (Garrett; 1981), the reliability index is calculated, which indicates a high validity as it is 0.93.

Statistical Techniques Used

In this study, the following statistical techniques were used for the analysis of data as Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentage, Critical ratio, ANOVA/F-ratio Post Hoc Analysis - Tukey - Kramer Method.

Objectives

1. To study the levels of the emotional intelligence among secondary school teachers.
2. To study the impact of the following variables on the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers.
 1. Gender 2. Locality 3. Age

Hypotheses

1. Secondary school teachers don't differ in their levels of the emotional intelligence.
2. The following variables don't make a significant difference in the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers.
 1. Gender 2. Locality 3. Age

Limitations of the Present study:

1. Some variables such as educational qualifications, marital status, religion, social status and other factors are not considered in the present study.
2. The geographical area is also limited to one district, i.e. East Godavari, Andhra Pradesh.
3. The size of the sample is restricted to 310 secondary school teachers.
4. The level of significance considered for testing the hypothesis is limited to 0.05.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

H₁: Secondary school teachers don't differ in their levels of the emotional intelligence.

Table 1: Classification of the Total Sample on the Emotional Intelligence

Sr. No.	Score	Size (N)	%	Verbal Description
		043	13.87	Low
	[[202	65.16	Moderate
	[[065	20.97	High
Total			100.00	

From table 1, it can be seen that nearly 14 % of the sample secondary school teachers have low emotional intelligence. Sixty-five percent of the sample has a moderate level and the remaining 21% of the samples have high emotional intelligence.

Table 2: Different Levels of Emotional Intelligence – Means – SDS - ANOVA

Age	N	Mean	S.D.	F-ratio	Results
126 and below scores (A)	043	118.02	7.17	541.11***	Sig. at 0.01 level
Between 127 and 153 scores (B)	202	138.35	7.00		
154 and above scores (C)	065	159.85	4.53		
ANOVA Summary					
Source of variation	SS	df	MS		
Between	46918.05	002	23459.03		
Within	13309.48	307	43.35		
Total	60227.54	309			

Table 2 shows that the obtained F ratio of 541.11 with $df = 2$ and 307 is higher than the critical value of 4.67, which is significant at the 0.01 level. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. It can be stated that secondary school teachers differ in their levels of emotional intelligence. Since the F ratio is significant, further analysis is needed to determine whether the levels of emotional intelligence groups are significantly different from other sub-groups.

Table 3: Different Levels of Emotional Intelligence - Post Hoc Analysis of HSD Statistic Using Tukey - Kramer Method

Levels of Emotional Intelligence		D	N ₁	N ₂	SE	Results
A	B	20.33	043	202	0.78	26.06***
A	C	41.83	043	065	0.92	45.46***
B	C	21.50	202	065	0.66	32.58***

*** Significant at 0.01 level

From table 3 Post-Hoc analysis using Tukey - Kramer HSD method, the obtained values (26.06, 45.46, and 32.58) with $df = 3$ and 310 are higher than the critical difference value of 4.12. They are significant at the 0.01 level. Therefore, the null hypotheses are rejected. Therefore, it can be inferred that secondary school teachers with the low level of emotional intelligence differ significantly from the moderate and high emotional intelligence of secondary school students, whereas secondary school teachers with the average level of emotional intelligence differ significantly from those with high achievement orientation of secondary school teachers.

H₂: Gender doesn't make a significant difference in the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers.

From table 6, the calculated *F ratio* (2.45, *df* = 3 & 306) is lower than the critical value of 2.64 at 0.05 level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. It can be assumed that age doesn't make a significant difference in the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers. *F ratio* is not significant at 0.05 level, no further probing of obtaining differences in different age groups in the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers.

Findings of this research

1. Nearly 14 % of the sample secondary school teachers have low emotional intelligence. Sixty-five percent of the sample has a moderate level and the remaining 21% of the samples have high emotional intelligence. The secondary school teachers differ in their levels of emotional intelligence.
2. Gender, locality and age doesn't make a significant difference in the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers.

Educational Implications:

Emotional intelligence is positively linked to career success and requires job satisfaction efforts to strengthen teachers' emotional intelligence through job training programs and effective guidance. Because personal differences in emotional intelligence persist and these differences are gender specific, locality specific and age specific. Uniform models of training programmes are not effective and therefore it is necessary to personalize training activities as much as possible. In order to strengthen the emotional intelligence aspects of secondary school teachers, guidance and counselling services should be made a part of school management.

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